

ON THE NUMBER OF SOLUTIONS OF A DIOPHANTINE EQUATION OVER A FINITE FIELD

Norichika Matsuki

3-9-34, Fujisaki, Narashino-shi, Chiba, Japan

n-matsuki@lime.plala.or.jp

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Abstract

We show that the number of distinct solutions of a Diophantine equation over a finite field is represented by the order and rank of a certain matrix derived from the coefficients.

1. Introduction

Let p be a prime, r be a positive integer, and F_q be a finite field with q = p^r elements. For f(x) = a_0x^{p-2} + a_1x^{p-3} + ... + a_{p-2} in F_p[x], define

A = (matrix with rows [a_0, a_1, ..., a_{p-2}], [a_1, a_2, ..., a_0], ..., [a_{p-2}, a_0, ..., a_{p-3}])

Kronecker (cf. [3, Chapter VIII, page 226]) showed that the number of nonzero solutions to f(x) = 0 equals p - 1 - rank A. In this paper we extend Kronecker's result to Diophantine equations in several variables over F_q.

First we give some notation and definitions. We denote by I_n the ideal (x_1^q - x_1, ..., x_n^q - x_n) of F_q[x_1, ..., x_n]. For f in F_q[x_1, ..., x_n], we define f-bar as the right-hand side of the congruence

f ≡ sum_{0 <= r_1, ..., r_n <= q-1} a_{r_1...r_n} x_1^{r_1} ... x_n^{r_n} (mod I_n).

Then it holds that f(b_1, ..., b_n) = f-bar(b_1, ..., b_n) for any b_1, ..., b_n in F_q. Here we denote by m_i = m_i(x_1, ..., x_n) the i-th monomial in the following chain of monomials, ordered in the graded lexicographic order

1 < x_1 < ... < x_n < x_1x_2 < x_1x_3 < ... < x_{n-1}x_n < ... < x_1^{q-1} ... x_n^{q-1}

and $c_i(\bar{f})$ by the coefficient of the monomial m_i in \bar{f} . Note that $c_i(\bar{f}) = 0$ if \bar{f} does not contain the monomial m_i . Then we define $K(\bar{f}) = (K(\bar{f})_{ij})$ as the $q^n \times q^n$ matrix whose (i, j) entry is $c_j(\overline{m_i f})$, namely,

$$K(\bar{f})_{ij} = c_j(\overline{m_i f}) = \sum_{\substack{t \in \{1, \dots, q^n\} \\ \text{s.t. } m_i m_t \equiv m_j \pmod{I_n}}} c_t(\bar{f}).$$

2. The Result

We shall introduce the basis to diagonalize $K(\bar{f})$ and show the spectrum of $K(\bar{f})$ coincides with the value set of f in the similar way as [4]. For our purpose, we need the following three lemmas. Although the first lemma is well-known, we give a proof for the sake of completeness.

Lemma 1. *The following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) $f(b_1, \dots, b_n) = 0$ for all $(b_1, \dots, b_n) \in \mathbb{F}_q^n$.
- (ii) $\bar{f} = 0$.

Proof. (ii) \Rightarrow (i) is obvious. For (i) \Rightarrow (ii), the proof given here is an adaptation of the proof of Lemma 2.1 in [1]. We use induction on n . It is obvious for $n = 1$.

Suppose that it is true for $n = k$ and that $f(b_1, \dots, b_{k+1}) = 0$ for all $(b_1, \dots, b_{k+1}) \in \mathbb{F}_q^{k+1}$. Write

$$\bar{f}(x_{k+1}) = \overline{a_{q-1}}x_{k+1}^{q-1} + \dots + \overline{a_1}x_{k+1} + \overline{a_0},$$

where $a_0, \dots, a_{q-1} \in \mathbb{F}_q[x_1, \dots, x_k]$. For each fixed $(b_1, \dots, b_k) \in \mathbb{F}_q^k$, it holds that $\bar{f}(b_{k+1}) = 0$ for all $b_{k+1} \in \mathbb{F}_q$. Hence $\overline{a_0}(b_1, \dots, b_k) = \dots = \overline{a_{q-1}}(b_1, \dots, b_k) = 0$ for all $(b_1, \dots, b_k) \in \mathbb{F}_q^k$. By the assumption, we have $\overline{a_0} = \dots = \overline{a_{q-1}} = 0$. Thus it is also true for $n = k + 1$. □

Lemma 2. *Let β be a generator of $\mathbb{F}_q^* = \mathbb{F}_q \setminus \{0\}$ and let*

$$w_i = (d_{i1}, \dots, d_{iq^n})$$

$$= \begin{cases} (1, \dots, 1) & \text{if } i = 1, \\ (\underbrace{0, \dots, 0}_{q^{i-2}}, \underbrace{\beta, \dots, \beta}_{q^{i-2}}, \dots, \underbrace{\beta^{q-1}, \dots, \beta^{q-1}}_{q^{i-2}}, \underbrace{0, \dots, 0}_{q^{i-2}}, \underbrace{\beta, \dots, \beta}_{q^{i-2}}, \dots) & \text{if } 2 \leq i \leq n, \\ (\underbrace{0, \dots, 0}_{q^{n-1}}, \underbrace{\beta, \dots, \beta}_{q^{n-1}}, \dots, \underbrace{\beta^{q-1}, \dots, \beta^{q-1}}_{q^{n-1}}) & \text{if } i = n + 1, \\ (m_i(d_{21}, \dots, d_{n+11}), \dots, m_i(d_{2q^n}, \dots, d_{n+1q^n})) & \text{if } n + 2 \leq i \leq q^n. \end{cases}$$

Denote by v_j the j -th column vector of the matrix whose rows are w_1, \dots, w_{q^n} . Then v_1, \dots, v_{q^n} are linearly independent over \mathbb{F}_q .

Proof. Suppose that in \mathbb{F}_q^n , we have $a_1w_1 + \dots + a_{q^n}w_{q^n} = 0$, where $a_1, \dots, a_{q^n} \in \mathbb{F}_q$. In other words,

$$a_1 + a_2d_{2j} + \dots + a_{q^n}d_{q^n j} = 0, \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq j \leq q^n.$$

By definition,

$$d_{ij} = m_i(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j}), \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq i, j \leq q^n,$$

so that the polynomial function defined by

$$g(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^{q^n} a_i m_i(x_1, \dots, x_n)$$

satisfies

$$g(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j}) = 0, \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq j \leq q^n.$$

Since, by construction, we have $\{(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j}) : 1 \leq j \leq q^n\} = \mathbb{F}_q^n$, it follows from Lemma 1 that $a_1 = \dots = a_{q^n} = 0$. Hence w_1, \dots, w_{q^n} are linearly independent over \mathbb{F}_q and so are v_1, \dots, v_{q^n} . \square

Lemma 3. $K(\overline{f})v_j = f(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j})v_j$.

Proof. Since

$$\begin{aligned} f(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j})d_{ij} &= f(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j})m_i(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j}) \\ &= \overline{m_i f}(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j}) = \sum_{k=1}^{q^n} c_k(\overline{m_i f})d_{kj}, \end{aligned}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} (K(\overline{f})_{i1}, \dots, K(\overline{f})_{iq^n})v_j &= (c_1(\overline{m_i f}), \dots, c_{q^n}(\overline{m_i f}))v_j \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{q^n} c_k(\overline{m_i f})d_{kj} = f(d_{2j}, \dots, d_{n+1j})d_{ij}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the lemma follows. \square

The formula for the number of solutions is derived immediately from these lemmas.

Theorem 4. Let $n(f)$ be the number of distinct solutions of $f \in \mathbb{F}_q[x_1, \dots, x_n]$. Then $n(f) = q^n - \text{rank } K(\overline{f})$.

Proof. Let $F : \mathbb{F}_q^{q^n} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_q^{q^n}$ be the linear map defined by $K(\overline{f})$. From Lemmas 2 and 3, we see that $\dim(\ker F) = n(f)$. By the rank-nullity theorem (e.g., [2, Chapter II, page 298]), it follows that $q^n = \text{rank } K(\overline{f}) + n(f)$. \square

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